

TEACHING ENGLISH TO PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN METHODS

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Abstract. *At present more and more parents want their children to start learning a foreign language (mostly English) before they go to school. In many kindergartens offer this possibility, some, particularly private ones, offer programs only in English. But these are just rare cases. Most often kindergartens provide an English course for their children as an extra curriculum activity once a week or once in 14 days.*

Key words: *foreign languages, possibility, preschool, method, kindergarten, English course, activity*

Teaching aids and materials. Grooming the spongy minds of kiddos to absorb the wonders of English takes a whole lot of patience and creativity. If you've taken language classes both as a child and adult, you'll know how vastly different your lessons might have been. Knowing how to teach English to young learners is a whole other ball game. Link language learning to physical activities by having children use and hear English for making things, drawing pictures, completing puzzles, labelling pictures, matching words and pictures, playing games, acting out movements in response to instructions and other activities that involve hands, eyes

and ears. Teachers often make use of TPR activities (activities based on linking language with actions, drawing on the method known as total physical response). Methods of learning English for children are based on 3 principles:

1. Interesting. Awaken the interest in the child's language - the main task of the teacher. Otherwise, the child will form a stereotype that English is and difficult
2. Sequence. You need to start with the basics. Attention needs all aspects simultaneously: grammar, conversation, reading
3. The game form. The main instrument of knowledge for the child is playing.

With its help to begin learning English for children the easiest way.

Teaching young learners English requires a host of games and activities. Engage your students on multiple levels, such as using fine and large motor movements, singing, talking, listening, and looking. For example, you could have a game where the students move around the room to stand next to a picture of the word you say, thus engaging them through listening, looking, and moving. Preschoolers are very visual. Bring in objects whenever possible. When it is impossible, find colorful and vivid pictures to use in place of the actual thing. Don't use the same game every time or let a game go on too long. You'll get bored and so will the students! That said, don't be afraid to repeat your students' favorite games that you know will always be a hit. The best ones are games that are adaptable to any topic or theme

Preschool students usually are not yet reading and writing (at least not to a large extent) in their language, so don't expect them to do it in a second language. At this age, you can expect them to listen and understand first. After a while, they will begin speaking individual words and short phrases.

I train kindergarten teachers in teaching English to pre-school children, and the teachers often ask me when the best time to start is. The public opinion tends to go in two opposite directions. Some say that teaching English to little children is rubbish, since they haven't fully mastered their mother tongue, that we steal their childhood away from them and so on. Others cannot wait to enroll their toddlers in the first course they can find. My experience so far makes me favour the golden mean. First and foremost, it needs to be said that activities linked to children's acquisition of a foreign language are not a burden to them, but rather an appealing game. Thoughts of "stolen childhood" are completely misguided. Children learn to use languages parallelly, so they do not need to wait until they have mastered one to start with the other. On the contrary, if they have problems pronouncing certain sounds, they might be stars of their English class since such pronunciation suits English very well.

The teaching of English to pre-school children is undoubtedly meaningful if it meets a natural development of a child and it is appropriate to his/her age. Moreover, it is successful if the teacher of English has adequate

knowledge of the target language, masters relevant methodology of teaching English at this stage of education, and s/he is enthusiastic about teaching young children. Then, it is also an asset for the child since s/he picks up the language in the same way as s/he acquires his/her native language.

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